

Notes

Complexes of Methylsalicylate and Ethylsalicylate with Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II)

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THE complexes of methylsalicylate with Ti^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} have been reported in literature. The formation of a series of Cu^{2+} complexes containing ethylsalicylate as ligand was reported by Graddon and Mockler¹. This prompted us to undertake the synthesis and structural studies of complexes of methylsalicylate and ethylsalicylate with Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} .

Experimental

Preparation of sodium salts of esters: Ester (0.1 mol) was dissolved in anhydrous benzene (50 ml) in 250 ml round bottomed flask and freshly cut sodium metal (4 g) was added to it. The contents of the flask were stirred to complete the reaction. At the end a slight excess of freshly cut sodium metal was added and stirred. Then the unreacted sodium metal was removed after washing with anhydrous benzene. The contents of the flask were transferred to 100 ml measuring flask with the help of absolute alcohol. The volume was made to the mark by the addition of absolute alcohol.

Preparation of complexes: The chlorides or acetates of the metals (0.01 mol) were dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol. To it was added sodium salt of the ester (0.02 mol) with constant stirring. The mixture was filtered after stirring for 1 h and the filtrate on evaporation yielded solid complex. The complex so obtained was washed with anhydrous benzene and dried.

Analysis of complexes: Zinc and cadmium were determined by pyridine thiocyanate method and mercury as HgS following the literature procedure.

Molar conductance measurement: A conductivity bridge model 31 manufactured by the Yellow Spring Instrument Co., U.S.A., was used for measuring the conductance of the solutions of the complexes in ethyl alcohol.

Infrared absorption measurements: A spectromom 2000 infrared spectrophotometer was used for recording the ir spectra of the complexes in nujol. The sodium chloride optics were employed while running the spectrum.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) show that the composition of the complexes is $M(OC_6H_4COOR)_2$,

where $M=Zn, Cd, Hg$, and $R=CH_3$ or C_2H_5 . All the complexes are white solids, soluble in methanol and ethanol but sparingly soluble in benzene and nitrobenzene. The low values of molar conductance in ethanol (Table 1) indicate the non-ionic nature of the complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL CONDUCTANCE AND INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA FOR COMPLEXES

Compd.	Metal %	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm^{-1}
	Found/(Calcd.)		
$Zn(O.C_6H_4COOCH_3)_2$	17.81 (17.79)	10.19	1560
$Cd(O.C_6H_4COOCH_3)_2$	26.21 (27.13)	9.71	1565
$Hg(O.C_6H_4COOCH_3)_2$	39.66 (39.86)	6.72	1555
$Zn(O.C_6H_4COOC_2H_5)_2$	15.96 (16.54)	9.13	1577
$Cd(O.C_6H_4COOC_2H_5)_2$	25.03 (25.41)	9.17	1575
$Hg(O.C_6H_4COOC_2H_5)_2$	37.07 (37.75)	8.44	1560

The infrared spectra have been employed to throw light on the nature of bonding in the complexes. The O—H stretching band appears at 3210 cm^{-1} in methylsalicylate and at 3205 cm^{-1} in ethylsalicylate. The comparison of the spectra of the complexes with those of the esters show the absence of O—H stretching band in the complexes. This clearly shows the involvement of the phenolic group in complexation when the O—H has been replaced by O—M bond. The second important absorption band, at 1684 cm^{-1} in methylsalicylate and at 1680 cm^{-1} in ethylsalicylate is due to C=O stretching mode. The corresponding absorption appears at lower frequency in the case of complexes (Table 1). This lowering of C=O stretching frequency on complexation suggests that there is coordination to the metal through the oxygen of the carbonyl group. The extensive lowering in C=O stretching frequency on coordination finds support from the study of earlier work where a shift of the order of 128 cm^{-1} was observed². Thus, the methylsalicylate and ethylsalicylate ions behave as bidentate ligands through the phenolate and carbonyl oxygen atoms. Keeping in view the metal to ligand molar ratio of 1 : 2, the metal ions may be assigned coordination number 4. The stereochemistry, possibly may be tetrahedral around the metal ions in the complexes. The thermodynamic stability constants at 25° in alcohol-water system (50 : 50 v/v) have been determined potentiometrically for these complexes. These values in the case of methylsalicylate for ML and ML_2 complexes in terms of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ are 6.52 and 5.90 for Zn^{2+} , 5.71 and 5.42 for Cd^{2+} , and 9.24 for Hg^{2+} whereas these values in the case of ethylsalicylate are 6.38 and 5.78, 5.59 and 5.25, and 9.17, respectively. The $\log k_2$ values for Hg^{2+} complexes could not be determined due to precipi-

tation. The observation of the lowering of C=O stretching frequency caused by complexation shows that it is in the order, $\text{Hg}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II} > \text{Cd}^{II}$. This is the same as the order found for the values of thermodynamic stability constants. Therefore, there exists a clear correlation between the lowering of C=O stretching frequency and the stability of the complexes. This can be explained on the basis of the strength of M—O bond. As the M—O bond becomes stronger the C=O bond lengthens and weakens. Hence, the C=O stretching frequency is lowered more. Similar reasoning has been used by Fujita *et al.*¹⁰ to explain bonding in metal oxalate complexes. Bellamy and Branch¹¹ have given a remarkable correlation between C=O stretching frequency and the stability constants for some complexes of salicylaldehyde with metal ions. Therefore, the correlation found in the present case also agrees with the earlier investigation.

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A New Method for the Preparation of Strontium Titanate and Strontium Hypovanadate

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STRONTIUM titanate has been a prized chemical by virtue of its dielectric¹, photoelectric² and surface properties³. The compound crystallises with the cubic perovskite structure⁴ as shown in Fig. 1. Till now only two techniques (and a few variants therein) have been employed for its synthesis, one of them is a solid state reaction⁵ between SrCO_3 and TiO_2 at 1100° , and the other is a coprecipitation⁶ of strontium titanyl oxalate followed by calcination at 850° . As ternary oxides, such as copper chromite, have been prepared by complex

formation, the present author found it interesting to apply this method to the preparation of strontium titanate. The most easily accessible and versatile complexing agent, EDTA, was used.

Fig. 1a. Perovskite crystal structure (with ion A at the body centre).

Fig. 1b. Perovskite crystal structure (with ion B at the body centre).

SrVO_3 is also a cubic perovskite containing vanadium in the B sites. It has been prepared earlier⁷ by solid state reaction between SrCO_3 and V_2O_5 in a current of H_2 . It was also proposed to prepare SrVO_3 by this complexing method.

All the chemicals used in the preparation were A.R. or of equivalent grade. For the preparation of Sr-EDTA complex, 7.35 g SrCO_3 and 14.6 g EDTA (free acid) were mixed and the mixture was taken into a well-stoppered polythene bottle. 150 ml water was added and the slurry gently shaken, taking care to allow the evolved CO_2 to escape smoothly. When the dissolution was complete, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 9 by the addition of NH_4OH . For the preparation of Ti-EDTA complex, 4 g TiO_2 was dissolved in about 40 ml HF and the mixture was cooled in ice. The supernatant liquid was tested for complete precipitation. The precipitate was filtered and washed free of F^- and NH_4^+ . It was then dissolved in minimum amount of dilute HCl and 14.6 g EDTA and 150 ml water were added to the solution. Preparation of the above two metal-EDTA complexes was carried out following the general procedure for the preparation of such complexes⁸.

The solutions of the above two metal-EDTA complexes were evaporated separately on a water bath to a small volume. The crystals were deposited from the solution by adding acetone. The supernatant liquid was drained and the crystals were mixed. The mixture was again dissolved in a minimum amount of water and allowed to evaporate. Cooling in ice or addition of acetone brought about crystallisation of the complexes in admixture. Before draining the supernatant liquid it was tested and the absence of both the metal ions in it was ensured. The crystals were dried and calcined in a mullite